

The Photochemical Decomposition of Nitrous Acid.

By K. S. MURTY AND N. R. DHAR.

Mukerji and Dhar (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1925, 31, 255) have shown that the decomposition of nitrous acid is markedly accelerated by light, and that the velocity coefficient both in light and in the dark increases slowly with the concentration of nitrous acid. The velocity coefficients are considerably greater (200-400 per cent.) when open vessels are employed instead of closed ones. This is ascribed to the escape of nitric oxide from open vessels. Mukerji and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the acceleration caused by light is more marked with closed than with open vessels.

In this communication, further results on the kinetics, temperature coefficients, quantum efficiency and the influence of the intensity of different wave-lengths are given.

The general experimental arrangement is the same as that described in a previous paper (Bhattacharya and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 148). A cubical quartz cell with plane parallel sides (4 cm.) served as the reaction vessel. Nitrous acid was prepared by the method described in a previous paper (Mukerji and Dhar, *loc. cit.*). The progress of the reaction was followed by determining the quantity of unchanged nitrous acid from time to time by the permanganate method.

Kinetics and Temperature Coefficients.

To obtain the regions of mean wave-lengths 4725 \AA and 7304 \AA respectively, a combination of two gelatine films, "Wallace M and S" filters, were used.

The experimental results are as follows.

TABLE I.

		<i>Dark.</i>			
Temperature	...	20°	30°	40°	50°
k_1 (monomolecular)	...	0.001882	0.002973	0.006552	0.012880
Temp. coefficient	...		1.58	2.21	1.95

TABLE II.

Region.	Temp.	k_1 (monomolecular).	k_1 (monomolecular after deducting dark reaction).	Temp. coeff. (without deducting the dark reaction).	Temp. coeff. (after deducting dark reaction).
Sunlight	30°	0.007505	0.004532		
Total light from a 1000-watt gas-filled tungsten filament lamp.	20°	0.003606	0.001724	1.55	1.52
	30°	0.005593	0.002620	1.50	0.69
	40°	0.008376	0.001824	1.51	0.22
	50°	0.013290	0.000410		
(5000-4450)Å. Mean 4725Å.	20°	0.003870	0.001488	1.56	1.53
	30°	0.005259	0.002279	1.55	0.69
	40°	0.008130	0.001578		
(5950-5450)Å. Mean 5650Å.	20°	0.002953	0.001071	1.56	1.53
	30°	0.004606	0.001633	1.66	0.69
	40°	0.007674	0.001122		
Mean 7304Å.	20°	0.002695	0.000813	1.56	1.50
	30°	0.004194	0.001231	1.77	0.69
	40°	0.007392	0.000840		
8500Å *	30°	0.003799	0.000826		

Determination of Quantum Yield.

The energy absorbed by the reactant was measured with a sensitive galvanometer (Hartmann-Braun) and a Moll-thermopile. The deflections of the galvanometer as read on the scale were calibrated by a Hefner-lamp (*cf.* Gehrlach, *Physikal Z.*, 1913, 14, 577).

The results are summarised in the following table.

TABLE III.

Temp.	Quantum yield for wave lengths (Å)			
	4725	5650	7304	8500
20°	10	9	4	—
30°	15	11	7	5
40°	8	7.8	1.2	—

* Blue cobalt glass cell filled with saturated potassium dichromate solution.

PHOTOCHEMICAL DECOMPOSITION OF NITROUS ACID 987

The influence of the variation of the intensity of incident light on the velocity of the photochemical decomposition of nitrous acid.

A screened Iris-diaphragm was placed between the source of light and the reaction vessel so as to avoid extraneous light from falling on the reacting system. The intensity of light was taken to be directly proportional to the area of aperture. In each case the extent of the reaction that would have taken place in dark was deducted from the total change observed in light, in order to obtain the change due to light alone.

TABLE IV.*

Temp. = 30°	A		B		C		k_1 (dark) = 0.002973
	1000 watt lamp.		4725 Å.		5550 Å.		
	k_1	k_1'	k_1	k_1'	k_1	k_1'	
Diameter of aperture (cm.).							
2	0.005393	0.002420	0.005179	0.00221	0.004592	0.00162	I
0.3	0.004544	0.001570	0.004505	0.00158	0.004035	0.00106	II
0.4	0.003969	0.001000	0.003876	0.00090	0.003536	0.00058	III

TABLE V.

	Ratio of velocities.	If proportional to \sqrt{I}	If proportional to $\sqrt[3]{I}$
A.	$\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.00242}{0.00157} = 1.5$	2.5	1.6
	$\frac{II}{III} = \frac{0.00157}{0.00100} = 1.6$	2.0	1.6
	$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.00242}{0.00100} = 2.4$	5.0	2.9
B.	$\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.00221}{0.00158} = 1.5$	2.5	1.8
	$\frac{II}{III} = \frac{0.00158}{0.00090} = 1.7$	2.0	1.6
	$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.00221}{0.00090} = 2.5$	5.0	2.9
C.	$\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.00162}{0.00106} = 1.5$	2.5	1.8
	$\frac{II}{III} = \frac{0.00106}{0.00058} = 1.8$	2.0	1.6
	$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.00162}{0.00058} = 2.8$	5.0	2.9

* In the above table k_1 , k_1' are the monomolecular constants calculated respectively from the observed data and for that corrected for the reaction in the dark.

It will thus be seen that the velocity of the photo-decomposition of nitrous acid is proportional to the cube root of the intensity of the incident light.

Discussion of Results.

An examination of Table I shows that the temperature coefficient of the thermal reaction increases from 1.58 (between 20° and 30°) to 2.21 (between 30° and 40°); between 40° and 50° there is a slight fall in the temperature coefficient, the value being 1.96. Similar increase in the temperature coefficient with elevation of temperature was noticed for this reaction by Ray, Dey and Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111. 413) and Mukerji and Dhar (*loc. cit.*). The latter workers obtained the following values:—

$$\frac{k_{20}^{\circ}}{k_{10}^{\circ}} = 1.1, \quad \frac{k_{30}^{\circ}}{k_{20}^{\circ}} = 1.5, \quad \frac{k_{40}^{\circ}}{k_{30}^{\circ}} = 1.9.$$

At first sight, this increase in the temperature coefficient with elevation of temperature would seem anomalous, as the temperature coefficient of most thermal reactions falls with temperature. But this can be explained as follows:—The decomposition of nitrous acid is a reversible reaction,

Any factor facilitating the escape of nitric oxide will produce an increase in the rate of decomposition of nitrous acid. The solubility of nitric oxide diminishes with the temperature. Two factors, thus contribute to the increase of velocity; one, the usual factor tending to increase the reaction velocity with the temperature; the other, the increasing facility for the escape of nitric oxide at higher temperature. Thus an abnormal increase in velocity with increasing temperature would be observed, and this results in the increase of temperature coefficient with the elevation of temperature.

It has been stated before that the temperature coefficients of the purely photochemical reaction in the various regions fall below unity in the temperature range 30° to 40° (*vide* Table II).

This is the reverse of the effect observed with most photochemical reactions. This may be due to either one or both of the two following factors. Firstly, there may be a decrease in absorption of light by the reacting system in passing from 30° to 40°; and

PHOTOCHEMICAL DECOMPOSITION OF NITROUS ACID 989

secondly the reverse reaction, the reduction of nitric acid by nitric oxide to nitrous acid ($\text{HNO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{NO} \rightleftharpoons 3\text{HNO}_2$) may be photochemical in nature and may be proceeding at a considerably greater speed at 40° than at 30°. Both factors seem to be at work in the case under consideration.

The results of absorption measurements tabulated below show a slight fall in the absorption.

Temperature.	Absorption corresponding to cm. on the scale.			
	Total light	4725Å	5650Å	7304Å
30°	26.56	6.98	5.18	6.49
40°	23.82	6.25	4.5	5.75

That the reverse reaction is also taking place photochemically with a greater speed at 40° than at 30° will be evident from the following considerations. If some of the absorbed light energy is utilised in the reverse reaction, then there should be an apparent reduction in the quantum yield for the direct reaction as passing from 30° to 40°. Experiments show that such is the case. To give an example, the quantum yield for the wave-length 7304Å is 7 at 30°, whereas at 40°, it is 1.2. The values of the quantum yield have been calculated on the assumption that the whole of the absorbed light energy is utilised in the direct reaction.

Only a few instances are on record where the temperature coefficients of a photochemical reaction are less than unity (Chapman and Gee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 1726; Trautz, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1915, 21, 336). Trautz (*loc. cit.*) worked at 18° and 98°. An increase in temperature of 80°, decreases the velocity of formation of sulphuryl chloride corresponding to a temperature coefficient of 0.88 per 10°. The explanation given above appears to be applicable to these cases also, because these reactions are also reversible.

Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence does not hold good for this photochemical reaction, which is exothermal in nature. Dhar (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, 21, 489) has emphasised that the law of photochemical equivalence usually fails in exothermal photochemical reactions.

Summary.

1. The decomposition of nitrous acid is markedly accelerated by light. The kinetics, temperature coefficients and energetics of this photochemical reaction have been studied in radiations of wave-lengths 4725Å, 5650Å, 7304Å and 8500Å.

2. The temperature coefficient of the thermal reaction increase from 1.58 between 20° to 30° to 2.21 between 30° to 40°. An explanation has been given for this anomalous increase of temperature coefficient with elevation of temperature.

3. The temperature coefficients of the purely photochemical reaction fall below unity in the temperature range 30° to 40° and 40° to 50°. A suitable explanation has been offered for this peculiarity.

4. The influence of varying the intensity of incident radiation on the velocity of this reaction has been studied. The monomolecular velocity coefficient has been found to be proportional to the cube root of the intensity.

5. This reaction does not follow Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
ALLAHABAD UNIVERSITY, ALLAHABAD.

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